

MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION AND VIBRO-ACOUSTIC ANALYSIS OF A PREIMPREGNATED CARBON FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY DRUM SHELL

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials are increasingly used in the production of musical instruments. This is due to the high stability against environmental conditions, lightweight and high mechanical properties. Instruments with harmonic patterns, as chordophones and idiophones currently apply the benefits of these materials. In the case of membranophones, composites are in their early stages, thus requiring an exhaustive study of vibro-acoustic behavior of these material parameters to understand their behavior in a "non harmonic" environment.

Characterization of material on the shell, and therefore modifying its mechanical properties, allows modulation frequencies generated by its vibrational modes. This fact gives us the possibility of intervening in the frequencies produced by the membranes that form the drum. In this work, the experimental and simulated data with Finite Element Analysis allows one to correlate the vibro-acoustic response of the preimpregnated composite laminate with the mechanical and material characterization.

For this purpose a experimental technique is proposed in order to match both results. A proper manufacturing study is also developed in order to establish appropriate material properties through its processing. The results show the vibro-acoustic analysis of a drum shell built in carbon fiber reinforced epoxy. A set of experiments conducted in different prototypes, illustrates variations in the frequencies produced by their vibrational modes depending on the wall thickness of the shell and the textile design definition.

1 INTRODUCTION

The industry of musical instruments is kept for years in continuous evolution. One of the lines of development in which manufacturers focus is the application of new materials, the reasons are to improve the reliability, durability and competitiveness. This is enabling expedite production processes, increase capacity to repeatability, prolong the life of the instruments, and generate new acoustical possibilities.

The importance of materials used in the manufacture of musical instruments rests largely on purely mechanical capabilities [1] that these present. On currently used materials such as wood, these mechanical capabilities are very often curtailed by environmental effects such as moisture and temperature, resulting in breakage of internal micro-fibers [2], and even sometimes severe deformities. This loss of mechanical and geometrical characteristics make it impossible to ensure acoustical stability in the musical instruments, so it becomes increasingly necessary to address new materials that present viable solutions to these problems. In this respect, instrument manufacturers of the family of string instruments, with harmonic character, such as violins, violas and cellos [3,4], have already opted

for the application of composite materials to manufacture their instruments giving satisfactory results, and consequently entering in the market as a viable alternative. In the family of membranophones instruments, although it is in its early stages, composite materials are presented as an alternative to materials traditionally used in the construction of drum shells, such as wood, metal or plastic. [5]. Drum shells from membranophones exert great influence on the timbre of the instrument [6] and the duration of the partial frequencies produced by the membranes. The use of composite materials immediately gives great technical advantages to instruments such as greater lightness and immunity to environmental effects, but besides this, they offer great potential for acoustical characterization.

In addition, the versatility of composites in the definition of its laminates will offer new degrees of freedom in specifying design variables as thickness, fiber orientation, selection of fabrics and resins, etc.

Figure 1: “Rasch Drums” Carbon Fiber Snare Drum.

Therefore, to control the timbre of membranophones is essential a thorough study of the lamination processes and how their mechanical characterization and production processes might affect the acoustical behavior of drum shells.

2 OBJECTIVE AND METHODOLOGY

The overall objective of this research is the analysis of possible variations produced in acoustic drum shell made of composite material due to the effect of changes in the laminate of this. To adjust the study to the reality of the current market will proceed to the analysis of a drum shell with standard dimensions available on the market, provided by a specialized manufacturer.

Figure 2: Processes of Prepreg and Laminate Production.

It is a laminated drum shell of carbon fiber - epoxy matrix prepreg processed by autoclave. This type of shell is ideal to ensure good results in research and obviating much of disabilities linked to this type of production processes. First, this is due to the choice of matrix, the epoxy resin has less curing

contraction between 1% and 2%, and lower coefficient of thermal expansion, $\alpha = 60 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$, compared to other matrices, which guarantees geometric stability needed for research. Secondly, preimpregnated fibers (prepreg) [8], which have a highly controlled manufacturing process as shown in Figure 2, facilitates correct alignment of the fibers in the laminate and provide a constant amount of resin per surface unit, this fact ensure constant thickness and mechanical capabilities. Finally the autoclave molding process [7,8] see figures 3,4 that due to the pressure during curing ensures proper fiber impregnation, a decrease in porosity and a perfect surface finish. It is a process and a high quality material used in the aerospace and automotive industries, and eventually into products that require greater control over the production process. Importantly drum shell given by the manufacturer contains a layer of polyurethane coating with thickness = 0.15mm, to be taken into account for the study.

Figure 3: Autoclave Laminate Process

Figure 4: Drum Shell molds

The methodology used to achieve the objectives set is to obtain natural resonance frequencies of the drum shell described above, using the simulated modal analysis by finite element method (FEA) and their comparison with experimental results. Although the reliability of simulations in modal analysis of composites [9,10] materials have been demonstrated above, the frequencies obtained by simulation [11] for each vibrational mode will be empirically tested to ensure its validity. Experimental tests consist in obtaining resonance frequencies through the drum shell by impact excitation and subsequent analysis of the obtained spectrum.

Finally we will apply changes in the characterization of the laminate, to thereby simulate by the same method variations in the frequencies obtained, the ratio of partial frequencies and its vibrational modes.

3 EXPERIMENTAL ACOUSTIC CHARACTERIZATION

The collection of frequencies generated by the drum shell it is obtained by recording controlled impacts. These impacts are made with Nylon drumsticks. [10] The shell is placed on a rigid support clamped by a point, in order not to interfere with the oscillatory motion of the latter. Recording is done in controlled and soundproofed environment, the sound system comprises a measurement microphone Behringer ECM8000 with flat spectrum connected to a computer with Audacity software. For the

experiment has taken the precaution of using a protected wiring thus avoiding interference of any kind.

Figure 5: (L) Experimental data (R) Complete Drum

Figure 6: (L) Spectrogram (R) Spectrum

4 NUMERICAL MODELING

4.1 Material Characterization

The drum shell material is characterized by a prepreg laminate consisting of 4 identical and collinear plies. Carbon Fiber Twill 4x4 ($280g/m^2$) with epoxy matrix.

Figure 7: (L) Carbon Fiber Twill 4x4 Fabric. (R) CFRE Drum Shell.

Diameter	354mm
Height	127mm
Thickness	1,51mm

Table 1: Dimensions of the Drum Shell

It is a fabric $0^\circ / 90^\circ$ and has the following properties:

Mechanical Tests	RT	Test Method
Tensile Strength (0°) (MPa)	817	ASTM D 3039
E_1 -Tensile Modulus (0°) (GPa)	56.6	ASTM D 3039
Tensile Strength (90°) (MPa)	835	ASTM D 3039
E_2 -Tensile Modulus (90°) (GPa)	55.9	ASTM D 3039
In-Plane Shear Strength (MPa)	128.2	EN 6031
G_{12} - In-Plane Shear Modulus (GPa)	3.5	EN 6031
ρ . Density (g/cm^3)	1.49	
ν . Poisson C.	0.06	[12]
V_f	0.5	
V_m	0.5	

Table 2: Characteristics of CFRE prepreg.

4.2 Simulation Data.

To obtain frequencies through simulation, we proceeded to 3D modeling of the piece with the drum shell dimensions described. We proceed to a simulation of natural frequencies for all frequencies generated by the vibrational modes of the geometry. Obtaining frequencies it is performed within the range of spectrum located between 1Hz - 1000 Hz}. [10] Once generated the geometry, the laminate is characterized by the following features:

Ply	Material	Thickness (mm)	α_1 / α_2 ($^\circ$)
0	Polyurethane	0.15	0
1	CFRE	0.34	0 / 90
2	CFRE	0.34	0 / 90
3	CFRE	0.34	0 / 90
4	CFRE	0.34	0 / 90

Table 3: Laminate Characterization

As can be observed, the outer layer corresponds to the outer coating present in used shell. It is a lacquer with $\rho = 0.92$ Density (g / cm³) and $E = 0.87$ GPa. The various layers of carbon fiber CFRE are defined as sheet using the data in Table 3, where $E_1 = 56.6$ GPa, $\nu = E_2 = 55.9$ 0.06 [12]. As used helmet laminate consists in 4 layers with a 0° angle to the direction of fiber 1, which involves a 90° angle to the direction of fiber 2. The thicknesses of each ply (0,34mm) they have been provided by the manufacturer of prepreg used in the manufacture of the drum shell.

Meshing is done following a cylindrical pattern such as that seen in Figure 8 where each element has a size of 4x4, with a maximum curvature deviation factor of 0.1.

Figure 8: Model Mesh

4.3 Results

The frequencies obtained are showed in the following table:

Mode	Nomenclature (m,n)	Simulated Data f (Hz)	Experimental Data f (Hz)
	(2,0) E	126.2	127
	(2,1) E	131.74	140
	(2,0) NE	195.79	199
	(2,1) NE	213.51	218
	(3,0)	393.45	406

	(3,1)	519.32	521
	(4,0)	563.97	583
	(5,0)	636.94	636
	(6,0)	716.11	719
	(4,1)	767.96	762
	(7,0)	829.71	825
	(8,0)	973.19	955
	(5,1)	1004.1	1024

Table 4: Comparison: Obtained frequencies and vibrational modes.

As can be observed in the lower frequency modes, the extensional modes [15, 16] are specified by the nomenclature, (m, n) E, as well as non extensional modes by (m, n) NE. There is agreement between the empirical and simulated data. It is seen in Figure 6, specifically in the mode (4,0) a maximum 2.74% error in Hz, an average value of 3,30Hz for the 13 vibrational modes located in the frequency range between {1 - 1000 Hz}. We conclude that the simulation is accurate enough to address new simulations with new material characterizations-

5 APPLICATION CASES

5.1 Vibroacoustic analysis with thickness increment.

In the following case study, a new characterization of laminate is simulated. The objective of this simulation is to understand the acoustic consequences of a laminate with an added ply. The new layer is identical to the previous and provides an increase of 0.34 mm to laminate.

The data obtained are:

Mode (m,n)	4 plies f_4 (Hz)	$f_{4mn}/f_{4(2,0)}$	5 plies f_5 (Hz)	$f_{5mn}/f_{5(2,0)}$	$f_5 - f_4$ (Hz)
(2,0) E	126.2	1	124.2	1	-2
(2,1) E	131.74	1,0439	128.35	1,0170	-3,39

(2,0) NE	195.79	1,5514	199.27	1,5790	3,48
(2,1) NE	213.51	1,6918	217.33	1,7221	3,82
(3,0)	393.45	3,1177	398.45	3,1573	5
(3,1)	519.32	4,1151	527.64	4,1810	8,32
(4,0)	563.97	4,4689	585.58	4,6401	21,61
(5,0)	636.94	5,0471	677.34	5,3672	40,4
(6,0)	716.11	5,6744	801.46	6,3507	85,35
(4,1)	767.96	6,0853	794.21	6,2933	26,25
(7,0)	829.71	6,5746	951.86	7,5425	122,15
(8,0)	973.19	7,7115	1140.7	9,0388	167,51
(5,1)	1004.1	7,9564	1072.4	8,4976	68,3

Table 5: Variation of the partial frequencies due to the increase in thickness

Analyzing the data we can observe, at first glance, generalized variations in the vibrational frequencies for all modes. Specifically, down and convergence between the extensional partial modes is observed. Moreover increased and separation of the frequencies produced by non extensional modes is observed. In turn type modes (m, 1) which have a nodal circle have a lower increase that those who have nodal lines only. Type (m, 0).

5.2 Vibroacoustic analysis changing orientation in plies 2 and 3.

In the following study case a new characterization of laminate is simulated. The objective of this simulation is to understand the acoustic effects resulting from changes in the orientation of the inner layers 2 and 3. Thus, the laminate case study is characterized by four equal plies to the original but with $\{0^\circ / 45^\circ / -45^\circ / 0^\circ\}$ pattern.

The results obtained are:

Mode (m,n)	$\{0/0/0/0\}f_0$ (Hz)	$f_0/f_{0(2,0)}$	$\{0/45/-45/0\}f_{45}$ (Hz)	$f_{45}/f_{45(2,0)}$	$f_{45} - f_0$ (Hz)
(2,0) E	126.2	1	229,8	1	103,6
(2,1) E	131.74	1,0439	241,94	1,0528	110,2
(2,0) NE	195.79	1,5514	246,85	1,0742	51,06
(2,1) NE	213.51	1,6918	263,2	1,1453	49,69
(3,0)	393.45	3,1177	587,92	2,5584	194,47
(3,1)	519.32	4,1151	728,66	3,1708	209,34
(4,0)	563.97	4,4689	879,79	3,8285	315,82
(5,0)	636.94	5,0471	1057,2	4,6005	420,26
(6,0)	716.11	5,6744	1150,2	5,0052	434,09

(4,1)	767.96	6,0853	1100,2	4,7876	332,24
(7,0)	829.71	6,5746	1198,4	5,2150	368,69
(8,0)	973.19	7,7115	1250,7	5,4426	277,51
(5,1)	1004.1	7,9564	1340,2	5,8320	336,1

Table 6: Partial frequency variations due to the change in orientation of the ply 2 and 3 of the laminate.

Analyzing the data we can observe at first glance generalized increases in the frequencies for all vibrational modes. These increases are significantly higher than in the case of increased thickness. It is further noted that the increase was positive and proportionally higher in extensional modes. (2.0 to 2.1). At no time exceeds the increase of 434.09 Hz mode (6.0).

Although there is an increase in the absolute values of the frequencies, a significant approach between the frequencies is observed, except that the extensional modes are separated slightly.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The initial examination of this document allows us to confirm the strong correlation between simulated and empirical data obtained. However there are small differences in the frequencies that will be further analyzed in order to increase the accuracy in future analysis.

This consistency in results has allowed us to develop a methodology to characterize acoustic drum shells accurately depending on the definition of composite laminates, this methodology will address new research in the future that will meet the interactions between membranes and shell according to the laminate. It will also be addressed in future experiments combinations with other materials such as aramid, glass fibers and biocomposites. In turn, it will be studied the viability of new production processes and influences that may cause on the acoustic characterization.

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